

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Djamolov Jumaboy Khissenovich

THE LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN "ON THE STATE LANGUAGE"

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

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